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Dynamic Mechanical Thermal Properties of Bagasse Fiber Reinforced Functionalized EPR Composites

Dinesh*, Sanjay Palsule

Department of Polymer & Process Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Roorkee, Saharanpur Campus, Saharanpur, 247001, India

*Corresponding author: Dinesh (dshkmr477@gmail.com)

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Introduction: Eco-friendly natural fibers offer low cost and are being used as reinforcement for polymer composites as a substitute for non-renewable conventional inorganic or synthetic fibers offering potential commodity, industrial and engineering applications (1). Thermoplastic elastomers (TPEs), being used for many applications, including automobiles, are expected to replace by reinforced TPEs. Being TPE, ethylene propylene rubber (EPR) is processable in the temperature range in which natural fibers are stable. Sugarcane bagasse has short fibers that offer good properties promoting wealth from waste when used as reinforcement for polymer composites. Natural fibers being hydrophilic show poor compatibility and poor adhesion with non-polar hydrophobic polymer matrix, resulting in adversely affecting the composite properties. Palsule process uses a functionalized polymer matrix that produces adhesion with natural fiber (2). In view of wealth from waste and reinforced TPEs being replacing TPEs for automobile applications, 15, 25 and 35 wt.% bagasse fibers (BGF) reinforced maleic anhydride functionalized EPR (CF-EPR) composites were developed by Palsule process and their mechanical properties and thermal properties have been reported (2). This study presents the dynamic mechanical thermal properties of the BGF/CF-EPR composites.

Methods: The detailed processing and sample preparation of the BGF/CF-EPR composites have been reported in our previous study (2). As per ASTM D5023-15, the dynamic mechanical thermal properties of the materials were studied by a DMA, Model 242C (NETZSCH) on 3 a point bending mode at 3°C/min from -125°C to +50°C using the samples of size 60mm x 13mm x 3mm at an amplitude of 10 µm and frequency of 1 Hz.

Results & Discussions: All the composites show marginally lower (T_g) (approx. -43°C) relative to the matrix (-37°C) because it has been reported that natural fibers contain some plasticizing components which get released during the processing and reduce the T_g of the composites (3). All the composites exhibit higher storage modulus (E') and higher loss modulus (E'') than the matrix. E' and E'' of the composites further improve with increasing fiber amount and confirm the good adhesion between BGF and matrix that improves with the increasing BGF amount in the composites. This adhesion imparts higher constraints to the motions of the components of the composites comparative to the matrix and increases the energy dissipation in composites. Cole-Cole plots, used to show homogeneity in composites, indicate that all the composites show proper dispersion and distribution of the fibers in them. Among them, the composite with the highest BGF content shows the highest homogeneity.

Conclusions: Present study reports the dynamic mechanical thermal properties of the BGF/CF-EPR composites that have been developed by Palsule process. Relative to the matrix polymer, all the composite compositions show marginally lower T_g but show higher E' and higher E'' that increases with the BG fiber contents in the composite compositions. Cole-Cole plots indicate homogeneity and proper dispersion of the BGF in the composites. The BGF/CF-EPR composites show a high premise and potential for industrial applications with good dynamic mechanical thermal properties.

Keywords: Bagasse Fiber, Functionalized EPR, Dynamic Mechanical Thermal Properties, Fiber/Matrix Interface

References

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